

released virions were stained with 2% phosphotungstic acid (PTA) and examined under electron microscope. The rod-shaped virions (Fig. 2) were 367.84 ± 26.85 nm long and 64.37 ± 5.63 nm wide.

This is the first known evidence of a nuclear polyhedrosis virus from *P. mathias* in the Philippines. □

2. Virions released from the polyhedra after 1-h treatment with 0.05 M NaCO₃ at 30°C. A) Virions in the polyhedral membrane; B) virions released from polyhedra.

Simulation of rice yield reduction caused by stem borer (SB)

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We adapted a rice crop growth model to simulate yield reduction caused by SB on irrigated IR64 at IRRI. Grain yield predicted by the model correlated well with yield obtained by clipping tillers in the field.

The computer simulations predicted that up to 20% deadhearts at the

vegetative stage would cause no significant reduction in grain yield— young plants could compensate for lost tillers. Damage at the grain filling stage (whiteheads) caused an almost proportionate yield reduction (see figure).

This suggests that spraying against SB at the early vegetative stage is often unnecessary, since young rice plants can tolerate considerable damage.

The computer simulations also suggest that yield reduction caused by SB is larger at low N levels since compensation then is less effective. Such physical factors as low radiation also can aggravate SB damage.

Simulated grain yield of IR64 in response to damage inflicted at 4 crop stages—active tillering (23 d after transplanting [DT]), maximum tillering (33 DT), panicle initiation (43 DT), and flowering (69 DT)—by clipping a fraction of tillers in each hill. Full lines (—) represent response when tillers are removed, dotted lines (· · ·) represent response when killed tillers are kept in place (natural stem borer damage). The difference is due to shading.

Life history of water strider *Limnogonus fossarum* (F.)

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L. fossarum is a common predator in wetland ricefields in the Philippines. An adult female water strider can consume up to 20 BPH a day.

We collected 100 eggs laid on cut TN1 rice stems. Emerging nymphs

Clipping tillers is an artificial method for mimicking deadhearts or whiteheads. It is relatively easy to carry out, but, unlike with natural SB damage, tillers removed by clipping no longer provide shade. We also used the model to compute how much results of experiments using the clipping method need to be adjusted to agree with natural SB damage (see figure).

Using the same model, similar field experiments and simulations were conducted at several research institutes under various weather conditions and using different varieties. Results confirmed that the model is not location specific. □

were released separately in 9-cm-diam petri dishes filled with distilled water and enclosed in 14-cm-high mylar cages with nylon mesh tops. Each cage contained cut TN1 stems and BPH for food. The cages were kept at 25–30 °C, 70–90% RH, and 12/24 h illumination.

As adults emerged, they were paired and kept inside 0.5-gal containers for oviposition. Survival and female fecundity were recorded daily.

Life cycle of the water strider was

57-66 d (Fig. 1). A female can lay as many as 87 eggs. Mean daily oviposition is shown in Figure 2. Mortality was highest at the 3d nymphal stage.

The species requires constantly flowing water, which is why it has low populations in ricefields. It also exhibits cannibalism. □

Integrated pest management – weeds

Weeds in direct seeded ricefields of Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu

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Weeds are a more serious problem in dry seeded rice than in wet seeded rice culture. We assessed weed species in direct seeded (dry seeded) rice 60 d after sowing in three cropping seasons: kuruvai (Jun-Jul to Sep-Oct) and thaladi (Sep-Oct to Feb-Mar) in double crop wetlands and samba (Aug-Sep to Jan-Feb) in single crop wetlands.

The major graminaceous weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli*, and *Chloris barbata*. The common Cyperaceae were *Cyperus rotundus*, *C. iria*, and *Fimbristylis miliacea*. Of nine families of dicots present, Onagraceae, Marsileaceae, and Asteraceae were important.

Weed density was highest during the samba season because of favorable moisture and climatic conditions (see table). Weed flora during kuruvai consisted of nearly equal densities of monocots and dicots. During thaladi and samba, monocots were dominant.

Irrespective of season, among the monocots *E. colona* was the major species (50-81%). *C. rotundus* (50-65%) dominated the sedges and *Ludwigia adscendens* and *Marsilea quadrifolia* (30-50%) dominated the broadleaf weeds. □

Fig. 1. Age-specific survival rate (lx) of the water strider *L. fossarum*, constructed using a life-table analysis, IRR, 1989. N = nymphal stage; $X = 60.25 \pm 1.18$.

Fig. 2. Average daily oviposition of water strider *L. fossarum*. IRR, 1989;

Weed density in direct seeded rice, Tamil Nadu, India.

Weed	Kuruvai		Thaladi		Samba	
	Density (no./m ²)	Relative density (%)	Density/m	Relative density (%)	Density/m	Relative density (%)
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	82	32.1	68	34.3	183	55.0
<i>E. crus-galli</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	8	3.1	28	14.1	18	5.4
<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	12	4.7	22	11.2	14	4.2
Others	3	1.2	21	10.6	12	3.6
Total grasses	105	41.3	139	70.2	227	68.2
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	16	6.3	8	4.0	20	6.0
<i>C. iria</i> L.	6	2.4	4	2.0	4	1.2
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	4	1.6	2	1.0	4	1.2
Others	5	2.0	3	1.6	5	1.5
Total sedges	31	12.2	17	8.6	33	9.9
<i>Ludwigia adscendens</i> (L.) Hara	42	16.5	12	6.2	38	11.4
<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i> L.	26	10.2	21	10.6	16	4.8
<i>Eclipta alba</i> (L.) Hassk.	18	7.2	4	2.0	9	2.7
Others	32	12.6	5	2.5	10	3.0
Total broadleaf weeds	118	46.5	42	21.2	73	21.9
Total weeds	254	100.0	198	100.0	333	100.0